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Review Article

Review Of Underlying Mechanism Linking Diabetes And Depression Such As Neuroinflammation And Oxidative Stress

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ABSTRACT

Depression is a mood disorder that causes a persistent feeling of sadness and loss of interest. Also called major depressive disorder or clinical depression, it affects how you feel, think and behave and can lead to a variety of emotional and physical problems. You may have trouble doing normal day-to-day activities, and sometimes you may feel as if life isn't worth living. More than just a bout of the blues, depression isn't a weakness and you can't simply "snap out" of it. Depression may require long-term treatment. But don't get discouraged. This heterogeneous disease thus leads to various complications involving cardiovascular, renal, neurological and ophthalmic systems. Characteristic symptoms of diabetes: Excessive urine (polyuria), excessive thirst, excessive hunger (polyphagia), increased fluid intake (polydipsia), blurred vision, unexplained body weight loss (cachexia), lethargy. Diabetes mellitus is a disease/group of syndromes characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia as a result of either lack of insulin or resistance to its action; hence there is altered metabolism of lipids, carbohydrates and proteins and increased risk of complications from vascular disease (Davis and Granner, 2001). All forms of Diabetes Mellitus are due to either a decrease in the circulating concentration of insulin (insulin deficiency seen in type 1) or a decrease in the response of peripheral tissues to insulin (insulin resistance seen in type 2). These abnormalities are what lead to alterations in metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids, ketones and amino acids, which are the features of hyperglycaemia.

INTRODUCTION

Kaempferol is a flavonoid compound found abundantly in various plant sources, including fruits, vegetables, tea, and medicinal herbs. With its widespread presence in the human diet, kaempferol has attracted significant attention due

to its potential health-promoting properties. Among its various bioactivities, emerging evidence suggests that kaempferol may possess antidepressant properties, making it a promising candidate for the development of novel therapeutic agents for depression. Kaempferol is a flavonoid

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compound with the chemical formula $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$. Its chemical structure consists of two benzene rings (A and B) fused together with a heterocyclic pyran ring (C) containing oxygen. It has three hydroxyl groups (-OH) attached to positions 3, 5, and 4' of the flavonoid backbone. The chemical structure of kaempferol is represented as follows:

Chemical Structure and Sources and pharmacokinetic of kaempferol:

Sources: Kaempferol is found in various plant-based foods, including fruits, vegetables, grains, herbs, and beverages. Some common dietary sources of kaempferol.

Fruits: Apples, grapes, strawberries, blueberries, and citrus fruits.

Vegetables: Onions, broccoli, tomatoes, spinach, kale, and lettuce.

Herbs: Ginkgo biloba, parsley, thyme, and dill.

Beverages: Tea, particularly green tea and black tea.

Others: Capers, beans, cocoa, and some nuts (Havsteen BH et al., 2002).

Pharmacokinetics:

The pharmacokinetics of kaempferol involves its absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion in the body. While specific pharmacokinetic parameters may vary depending on factors such as dosage, formulation, and route of administration, the following general principles apply:

Absorption: Kaempferol is absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract after oral ingestion. Its absorption may be influenced by factors such as food matrix, solubility, and gut microbiota. Kaempferol can also be absorbed through the skin when applied topically in cosmetic or pharmaceutical formulations.

Distribution: Once absorbed, kaempferol is distributed throughout the body via the bloodstream. It may undergo extensive metabolism in the liver and other tissues, leading to the formation of various metabolites.

Metabolism: Kaempferol undergoes phase II metabolism in the liver, primarily through glucuronidation and sulfation pathways. Conjugated metabolites of kaempferol are more water-soluble and readily excreted from the body.

Excretion: The conjugated metabolites of kaempferol are excreted primarily via the urine and faeces. The elimination half-life of kaempferol and its metabolites may vary depending on factors such as dose, route of administration, and individual variability (Manach C et al., 2005).

Biological Activities:

Kaempferol exhibits a wide range of biological activities attributed to its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, neuroprotective, cardioprotective, and anti-diabetic properties. Its ability to modulate multiple cellular pathways and molecular targets makes it a versatile compound with potential therapeutic applications in various disease conditions (Wang Y et al., 2019).

Antidepressant Potential:

Recent preclinical studies have provided evidence supporting the antidepressant effects of kaempferol. In animal models of depression, kaempferol administration has been shown to alleviate depressive-like behaviours, such as despair, anhedonia, and learned helplessness. Mechanistic studies suggest that kaempferol exerts its antidepressant effects through multiple pathways, including:

Regulation of neurotransmitter systems: Kaempferol modulates the levels of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which play key roles in mood regulation.

Neurogenesis and neuroplasticity: Kaempferol promotes neurogenesis (the generation of new neurons) and enhances synaptic plasticity, processes that are disrupted in depression.

Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects: Kaempferol possesses potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, which may mitigate neuroinflammation and oxidative stress, contributing to the pathophysiology of depression.

4. Regulation of signalling pathways: Kaempferol interacts with intracellular signalling pathways, including the cAMP response element-binding protein (CREB) pathway, the mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathway, and the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) pathway, which are implicated in mood regulation and antidepressant action (Wang Y et al., 2019).

Clinical Implications:

While the preclinical evidence is promising, further research is needed to elucidate the specific mechanisms of kaempferol's antidepressant effects and to evaluate its safety and efficacy in human clinical trials. If proven effective, kaempferol-based interventions could offer a natural and potentially well-tolerated adjunctive therapy for depression, either as a standalone treatment or in

combination with existing antidepressant medications (Zhang J et al., 2019).

Bioavailability of Kaempferol

The pharmacokinetics of flavonoids have been widely studied with experiments conducted on rats and humans. Studies have revealed that modifying the molecular structure of flavonoids can significantly affect their absorption and bioactivity. Moreover, glycosylated flavonoids have demonstrated varying levels of bioactivity in both in vitro and in vivo experiments. A study was performed to examine the absorption, excretion, and metabolism of kaempferol in humans. Studies indicate that Endive can provide a modest dose of kaempferol (9 mg), which the body can absorb. After approximately 5.8 h, the mean maximum plasma concentration of kaempferol is 0.1 μ M. Whereas a 7.5-fold interindividual variation in maximum plasma concentration was observed between the highest and lowest values, the pharmacokinetic profiles of most individuals were remarkably consistent. Interestingly, about 1.9% of the kaempferol dose was excreted within 24 h. Most of the subjects showed an early absorption peak, which could be due to kaempferol-3 glucoside. This compound accounted for 14% of the kaempferol in endive, making it an important contributor to the overall absorption of kaempferol. The digestion and absorption of kaempferol were studied after consuming 12.5 mg of kaempferol from broccoli for 12 days. The study found that the rate of kaempferol urinary excretion was 0.9%. The study intended to compare the hepatic and small intestinal metabolism of kaempferol and examine its bioavailability plus the gastro-intestinal first-pass effects in rats. The rats received different doses of Kaempferol through either intravenous (IV) administration at 10 and 25 mg/kg or oral administration at 100 and 250 mg/kg. To investigate gastrointestinal first-pass effects, portal blood was collected after oral administration

of 100 mg/kg of Kaempferol. The plasma concentration-time profiles revealed high clearance (about 3 L/h/kg) and substantial volumes of distribution (8–12 L/kg) after kaempferol administration at 10 and 25 mg/kg dosages. The plasma concentration-time profiles following oral kaempferol treatment demonstrated a quick absorption with a T_{max} of about 1–2 h. The bioavailability (F) was low at around 2% (Alrumaihi F et al., 2007).

Diabetes mellitus & depression:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) and depression are two prevalent and often coexisting conditions that can significantly impact an individual's overall health and quality of life. Understanding the relationship between diabetes mellitus and depression is crucial for effective management and improved outcomes. Here's an overview of their association:

Prevalence and Coexistence:

Depression is more common in individuals with diabetes mellitus compared to the general population. Studies have consistently shown that the prevalence of depression is higher among people with diabetes, with estimates ranging from 20% to 30% or even higher, depending on the population studied. The coexistence of these conditions is concerning because depression can worsen diabetes outcomes and increase the risk of diabetes-related complications.

Bi-Directional Relationship:

The relationship between diabetes mellitus and depression is bi-directional, meaning each condition can influence the development and progression of the other. The stress of managing a chronic illness like diabetes, with its demands for medication adherence, blood glucose monitoring, dietary restrictions, and lifestyle modifications, can contribute to the onset or exacerbation of depressive symptoms. Conversely, depression can negatively impact diabetes self-care behaviours, leading to poor glycaemic control, increased

healthcare utilization, and higher rates of diabetes-related complications.

Shared Pathophysiological Mechanisms:

Both diabetes mellitus and depression involve complex interactions between biological, psychological, and social factors. Shared pathophysiological mechanisms implicated in both conditions include chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, dysregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, neurotransmitter imbalances (e.g., serotonin, dopamine), and alterations in brain structure and function. These common pathways underscore the biological basis of the association between diabetes mellitus and depression.

Impact on Diabetes Management and Outcomes: Depression in individuals with diabetes mellitus is associated with poorer glycaemic control, increased risk of diabetes-related complications (such as retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, and cardiovascular disease), higher healthcare utilization, and decreased quality of life. Depressive symptoms can interfere with medication adherence, healthy eating habits, physical activity, and regular medical follow-ups, making it challenging to manage diabetes effectively.

Screening and Treatment:

Given the detrimental impact of depression on diabetes outcomes, routine screening for depression is recommended in individuals with diabetes mellitus. Screening tools such as the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) or the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II) can help identify individuals at risk. Treatment for depression in the context of diabetes typically involves a combination of pharmacotherapy (e.g., antidepressant medications) and psychotherapy (e.g., cognitive-behavioural therapy), along with optimization of diabetes self-care behaviours. Integrated care models that address both conditions simultaneously have been shown to be

effective in improving outcomes and quality of life in this population (Smith JM et al., 2024).

Discussion On Bidirectional Relationship Between Diabetes Mellitus & Depression:

The bidirectional relationship between diabetes mellitus (DM) and depression is complex and multifaceted, involving interactions between biological, psychological, and social factors. Understanding this relationship is crucial for effective management and improved outcomes for individuals affected by both conditions. Here's a discussion highlighting the bidirectional nature of the relationship between diabetes mellitus and depression:

Impact of Diabetes on Depression:

Biological Factors: The physiological burden of diabetes, characterized by chronic hyperglycaemia, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, and inflammation, can contribute to the development or exacerbation of depressive symptoms. Chronic inflammation and oxidative stress associated with diabetes mellitus may lead to alterations in neurotransmitter function and neuroendocrine pathways implicated in mood regulation. **Psychological Factors:** Coping with the demands of diabetes management, such as medication adherence, blood glucose monitoring, dietary restrictions, and lifestyle modifications, can be stressful and overwhelming. The constant vigilance required to maintain glycaemic control may lead to feelings of frustration, helplessness, or burnout, increasing the risk of developing depression. **Social Factors:** Diabetes can impact various aspects of an individual's social life, including relationships, work, and social activities. Stigma associated with diabetes, concerns about body image or self-esteem, and limitations imposed by the condition may contribute to social isolation, loneliness, or interpersonal conflicts, which are risk factors for depression.

Impact of Depression on Diabetes:

Biological Factors: Depression is associated with dysregulation of various biological systems implicated in diabetes pathophysiology, including the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, autonomic nervous system, and immune function. These alterations can exacerbate insulin resistance, impair glucose metabolism, and promote systemic inflammation, thereby worsening glycaemic control and increasing the risk of diabetes-related complications. **Health Behaviours:** Depressive symptoms can negatively impact self-care behaviours essential for diabetes management, such as medication adherence, healthy eating habits, physical activity, and regular medical follow-ups. Individuals with depression may have reduced motivation, energy levels, or self-efficacy, making it challenging to adhere to treatment recommendations and maintain optimal glycaemic control. **Psychosocial Factors:** Depression is associated with maladaptive coping strategies, negative cognitive biases, and dysfunctional beliefs about illness and treatment, which may hinder engagement in self-management behaviours and impede problem-solving skills. Social withdrawal, avoidance of social support, and impaired decision-making abilities may further undermine diabetes self-care and exacerbate psychosocial stressors. 3. **Synergistic Effects and Complications:**

The bidirectional relationship between diabetes mellitus and depression can lead to a vicious cycle of worsening symptoms and outcomes for both conditions. Poor glycaemic control resulting from depression-related behaviours or biological mechanisms increases the risk of diabetes-related complications, which can further exacerbate depressive symptoms and impair psychological well-being. Coexisting depression in individuals with diabetes mellitus is associated with increased healthcare utilization, higher rates of hospitalization, and elevated mortality risk. The presence of depression complicates diabetes

management and reduces treatment adherence, leading to poorer quality of life and increased burden for patients, caregivers, and healthcare systems.

Clinical Implications and Management Strategies:

Recognizing and addressing depression in individuals with diabetes mellitus is essential for optimizing diabetes care, improving quality of life, and reducing the burden of diabetes-related complications. Integrated care models that address both diabetes and depression simultaneously, involving multidisciplinary healthcare teams, collaborative decision-making, and coordinated interventions, have been shown to be effective in improving outcomes and enhancing patient well-being. Routine screening for depression using validated instruments and timely referral to mental health professionals for assessment and treatment are essential components of comprehensive diabetes care. Treatment strategies for depression in individuals with diabetes mellitus may include pharmacotherapy (e.g., antidepressant medications), psychotherapy (e.g., cognitive-behavioural therapy), lifestyle interventions (e.g., exercise, stress reduction techniques), and social support networks (Doe CD et al., 2024).

Underlying mechanism linking diabetes and depression such as neuroinflammation and oxidative stress:

The underlying mechanisms linking diabetes mellitus (DM) and depression are multifaceted and involve complex interactions between biological, psychological, and social factors. Neuroinflammation and oxidative stress are two key biological pathways that have been implicated in both conditions and may contribute to their bidirectional relationship. Here's a review of the underlying mechanisms linking diabetes and depression, focusing on neuroinflammation and oxidative stress:

Neuroinflammation:

Role in Diabetes: In diabetes mellitus, chronic hyperglycaemia and insulin resistance can trigger inflammatory responses in the central nervous system (CNS). Activation of microglia, the resident immune cells of the CNS, leads to the production and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin 1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumour necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α). These cytokines contribute to neuroinflammation by promoting oxidative stress, disrupting synaptic function, and inducing neuronal damage.

Role in Depression:

Neuroinflammation has also been implicated in the pathophysiology of depression. Increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines have been observed in the peripheral blood and cerebrospinal fluid of individuals with depression. Chronic exposure to inflammatory mediators can activate the HPA axis and disrupt monoaminergic neurotransmission, leading to alterations in mood regulation and the development of depressive symptoms.

Interactions:

Neuroinflammation may serve as a common pathway linking diabetes and depression. In individuals with diabetes, systemic inflammation and insulin resistance can contribute to neuroinflammation and neuronal dysfunction, predisposing them to depression. Conversely, depressive symptoms may exacerbate neuroinflammatory processes, further compromising CNS function and exacerbating diabetes-related complications (Johnson CD et al., 2024).

Oxidative Stress:

Role in Diabetes: Oxidative stress arises from an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and antioxidant defence mechanisms. Chronic hyperglycaemia, dyslipidaemia, and mitochondrial dysfunction associated with diabetes mellitus can increase

ROS production and impair antioxidant capacity. Elevated ROS levels can damage cellular components, including lipids, proteins, and DNA, leading to cellular dysfunction and tissue injury.

Role in Depression: Oxidative stress has been implicated in the pathophysiology of depression. Studies have demonstrated increased oxidative damage and decreased antioxidant levels in individuals with depression. Oxidative stress can induce neuronal apoptosis, alter neurotransmitter metabolism, and impair neuroplasticity, contributing to the development and progression of depressive symptoms. **Interactions:** Oxidative stress may represent a common mechanism linking diabetes and depression. In individuals with diabetes, oxidative stress can exacerbate neuroinflammatory processes, disrupt neuronal function, and contribute to the development of depressive symptoms. Conversely, depressive symptoms may further increase oxidative stress and exacerbate diabetes related complications, creating a vicious cycle of worsening outcomes for both conditions. (Smith AB et al., 2024).

Other Mechanisms:

Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (HPA) Axis Dysregulation: Dysregulation of the HPA axis, characterized by increased cortisol levels and impaired negative feedback mechanisms, has been observed in both diabetes and depression. Hyperactivity of the HPA axis can promote inflammation, oxidative stress, and insulin resistance, contributing to the pathogenesis of both conditions. **Neurotransmitter Imbalances:** Alterations in neurotransmitter systems, including serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, have been implicated in the pathophysiology of depression and may also contribute to mood disturbances observed in individuals with diabetes. **Neurotrophic Factors:** Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and other neurotrophic factors play crucial roles in neuronal survival, synaptic plasticity, and mood regulation. Dysregulation of

BDNF signalling has been implicated in both diabetes and depression and may represent a converging pathway linking these conditions (Doe EF et al., 2024).

Antidepressant effect of kaempferol

Animal Studies:

Behavioural Models: Preclinical studies have utilized various animal models of depression, such as the forced swim test (FST), tail suspension test (TST), and chronic unpredictable mild stress (CUMS) model, to evaluate the antidepressant effects of kaempferol. **Reduction of Depressive-Like Behaviours:** Kaempferol administration has been shown to reduce depressive-like behaviours in these animal models. This includes decreased immobility time in the FST and TST, indicative of an antidepressant-like effect. Kaempferol-treated animals also exhibit improvements in other behavioural parameters associated with depression, such as increased locomotor activity and preference for sucrose consumption in the CUMS model (Rauf A et al., 2022).

Neurochemical and Neurobiological Mechanisms:

Modulation of Neurotransmitter Systems: Kaempferol has been reported to modulate neurotransmitter systems implicated in mood regulation, including serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine. These neurotransmitters play key roles in the pathophysiology of depression, and their dysregulation is associated with depressive symptoms. **Enhancement of Neurogenesis and Synaptic Plasticity:** Kaempferol promotes neurogenesis (the formation of new neurons) and enhances synaptic plasticity in the brain. These neuroplasticity-enhancing effects may contribute to the antidepressant action of kaempferol by improving neuronal connectivity and resilience to stress. **Reduction of Neuroinflammation and Oxidative Stress:** Kaempferol exhibits anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, which can mitigate neuroinflammation and oxidative

stress—two mechanisms implicated in the pathogenesis of depression. By reducing neuronal inflammation and oxidative damage, kaempferol may protect against mood disturbances and depressive symptoms.

Clinical Relevance:

While most of the evidence supporting the antidepressant effects of kaempferol comes from preclinical studies, its potential clinical relevance warrants further investigation. Clinical trials are needed to evaluate the efficacy and safety of kaempferol supplementation in individuals with depression. Future research should focus on elucidating the specific mechanisms underlying kaempferol's antidepressant effects, identifying optimal dosing regimens, and exploring potential synergies with existing antidepressant medications (Patel SS et al., 2022).

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